

Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Databases and Approaches: A Systematic Review

¹ Simran N. Maniyar, ² Dr. Sonali Kulkarni

^{1 & 2} Department of Computer Science and IT, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, chhatrapati Sambhajinagar

Abstract

Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) is a highly dynamic subject within Natural Language Processing (NLP) that exhibits significant life. SA entails computationally processing or categorising user sentiments, views, and emotions embedded in text. The essential and thoroughly explored phase of SA is aspect extraction, which is critical for accurately and precisely identifying feelings. The extraction of aspects has evolved as a vital stage in Sentiment Analysis (SA) throughout the last decade, playing a critical role in obtaining concise sentiment classification. This study focuses on aspect extraction approaches, specifically determining the best technique for a given database. The goal is to assess various database strategies and select the best option.

Keywords: Sentiment analysis, Feature Extraction, NLP

I. Introduction:

Sentiment analysis (SA), also known as opinion mining (OM), is the process of recognising and extracting user feelings or emotions from numerous platforms such as blogs, social media sites, discussion forums, merchant or manufacturer websites, and others. With the growth of international e-commerce in recent years, many people now make internet buying a daily ritual. As a result, a plethora of reviews on various goods and services have surfaced, each of which captures the subtle linguistic variations across various nations. Sentiment analysis is useful in developing economic and marketing strategies, particularly in marketing environments. It aids in determining the popularity of various product or service versions and identifying demographics interested in specific features. Despite its benefits, sentiment analysis has limitations, such as the subjective character of opinion words, which might change in positive or negativity depending on context. Furthermore, the different expression of thoughts and the fusion of opposing viewpoints within a single statement, particularly in informal media such as Twitter or blogs, make it challenging for computers to effectively detect sentiments [3].

Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) is essential in this context for helping customers make wise purchasing decisions. Furthermore, ABSA helps businesses and retailers to better grasp their advantages, disadvantages, and market needs [8]. One subtler element of sentiment analysis (SA) is Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA), also known as target-specific sentiment classification. Its main goal is to identify a deep and all-encompassing sentiment polarity in a text sequence that is directed towards a particular aspect, which frequently takes the form of aspect phrases that are mentioned explicitly [9].

Aspect phrase extraction and aspect term categorization are the two basic procedures that are usually involved in aspect-based sentiment analysis. The important topics in the text are found during the aspect extraction stage. This task entails identifying elements and properties of a target entity from the review. For example, "iPhone camera quality is amazing," the aspect extraction operation will locate aspect as "camera quality" of entity "iPhone." These aspects are divided into three categories during the aspect classification phase: positive, negative, and neutral [12].

A systematic review was designed utilising criteria for performing a management systematic literature review. To begin, we define the research question. Continue by retrieving and selecting potentially related literature. We then synthesise relevant material from the literature before reporting the review's findings. The following research question was answered to provide an overview of the review:

- RQ1: Which approach is used to perform sentiment analysis on social media that is aspect-based?
- RQ2: Which social media platform category is most frequently used for sentiment analysis databases?

a. Sentiment analysis resources:

Sentiment analysis primarily aims to collect data. It does so by tapping into social communication channels like Twitter and Facebook, or by utilizing pre-existing resources.

Figure 1 : sentiment analysis data sources

- I. **News Articles:** Sentiment analysis is frequently used to analyse news pieces, including financial reports and political analyses. The literary format of these papers is often formal and structured [Reference 1].
- II. **Reviews:** Due to their importance in understanding thoughts and sentiments, numerous studies have concentrated solely on reviews. When doing their research, researchers frequently give priority to the analysis of movie and product reviews in order to acquire responses and gauge feelings [2].
- III. **Feedback:** Feedback is a crucial tool for both professional and personal growth. It can take many different forms, such as constructive criticism and positive reinforcement. Specific, timely, and balanced
- IV. feedback that addresses both strengths and potential improvement areas is what constitutes effective feedback. Feedback at work aids in evaluating worker performance and promoting development. It promotes comprehension, communication, and conflict resolution in both relationships and education [3].
- V. **Blogs and forums:** Blogs and forums are excellent sources of ideas and feelings that offer crucial data for research. By perusing blogs and web forums, researchers can get this data. Forums are frequently specialised to particular topics, guaranteeing sentiment analysis in a single domain. The daily insights and reviews that bloggers often add to their content are relevant to their local, national, and international experiences.
- VI. **Social Networks :** Sentiment analysis can benefit greatly from the wealth of opinions and reviews available on social networking sites like Twitter and Facebook:
 - Twitter: Users exchange 140-character-maximum tweets, which are brief messages. These tweets are a great resource for reviews and perspectives. Twitter is a microblogging platform that makes it possible to gather user opinions, assisting in the discovery of new trends and poll findings.
 - Facebook: Launched in 2004, this hugely popular social network enables members to upload personal profiles, images, videos, and other relevant content. This vast body of user-generated content is a useful source for sentiment analysis because it gives computers the data they need to interpret the hidden feelings in human communications.

II. Literature Review:

Ashmaki Suresh Waydande et.al: In the paper author used, various approaches to feature selection and their corresponding data sources and accuracy rates are presented. The approaches include Lexical Resource and Apriori, utilizing Amazon customer reviews with an accuracy of 87.07%. The Lexical Approach employs Graph Distance Measurement using user blog posts, achieving an accuracy of 82.85%. The Hybrid n-gram method is based on movie-based reviews, attaining an accuracy of 90.05%. Naive Bayes with Information Gain is applied to canteen services reviews, yielding an accuracy of 91.75%. Additionally, a combination of Naive Bayes and SVM, based on minimum cuts, is used for movie reviews from users, resulting in an accuracy of 85.90%. Lastly, the Proposed Approach combines NLP and ML for specific product-based reviews, achieving an impressive accuracy rate of 95.20%. [3].

Amani K Samha et.al: Author work on data the dataset consists of 2,500 sentences from customer reviews of five products, initially gathered from Amazon.com and Cnet.com, and processed by Hu and Liu. It includes over 260 opinionated reviews, manually tagged for aspects and opinions. In aspect extraction and opinion extraction, the F-measure is used to evaluate the performance of both the Baseline [2] and the proposed technique. The Baseline [2] achieves an F-measure of 0.74 for aspect extraction and 0.65 for opinion extraction. In contrast, the proposed technique demonstrates improved performance with an F-measure of 0.77 for aspect extraction and 0.60 for opinion extraction. These F-measure values indicate that the proposed technique outperforms the Baseline [2] in aspect extraction while maintaining a similar level of performance in opinion extraction.[4]

Hongjie Cai et.al : Author worked on The "Multi-Element Multi-Domain dataset (MEMD)," which includes over 20,000 review phrases and 30,000 quadruples annotated with both explicit and implicit aspects and opinions for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) research, is the dataset that is being discussed. It spans four elements across five domains. Performance indicators for several models across five domains (Books, Clothing, Hotel, Restaurant, and Laptop). RoBERTaABSA routinely achieves the greatest scores across the majority of the measures, including Accuracy (ACC) and Macro-F1 scores, demonstrating its strong performance in aspect-based sentiment analysis.[5]

JIANGTAO HE et.al: They research on the critical interaction between global context and attributes is not given enough attention. Furthermore, research in Chinese ABSA and multilingual ABSA is lacking, necessitating creative solutions. For this author Utilising three Chinese comment datasets (Camera, Phone, and Car) with Positive and Negative sentiment categories, our study evaluated the performance of our LGCF model. The SemEval-2014 Laptop and Restaurant datasets, SemEval-2016 Restaurant dataset , and an ACL Twitter social dataset were added to our evaluation. These tests were designed to show how well the model handled a variety of sentiment analysis tasks. They present the LGCF model, devoted to aspect-based sentiment analysis, to overcome these problems [6] .

Waqas Ahmad et.al: The study uses seven common datasets provided by SemEval to evaluate a methodology. These datasets include reviews of laptops and restaurants from SemEval-14, as well as additional restaurant and laptop data from SemEval-15 and SemEval-16. The Twitter-Crude oil dataset, which consists of 1000 tweets regarding the views of investors on crude oil, is also included in the study. This dataset was developed in 2020 by Yassine Hamdaoui. The study evaluates the performance of the methodology across several domains, with a particular emphasis on the Twitter-Crude oil dataset for validation. With the help of word2vec embedding, contextual positioning, and tree-based structures, the Attention-based MC-CNN can better identify aspects and sentiment in text reviews. When compared to single-feature models, our method captures intricate semantic links between words, leading to more accurate sentiment categorization and higher resilience.[7]

JIANGTAO HE et.al :Their study examined the performance of the LGCF model using a variety of datasets, including the SemEval-2014 and SemEval-2016 restaurant datasets, an ACL Twitter dataset, a T-shirt dataset, a television dataset, and three Chinese comment datasets (Camera, Phone, and Car) with binary sentiment (Positive and Negative). Comparing LGCF to a number of well-established state-of-the-art models, significant performance and

efficiency improvements have been made. Additionally, the outcomes of ablation tests confirm the effectiveness of each LGCF component[8].

JINDIAN SU et.al : They focus on Traditional feature-based neural approaches to aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) rely on pre-trained word embeddings and aspect-text relations, but they have problems with aspect-awareness, task agnosticism, and domain knowledge. This study offers BERT4ABSA, a BERT-based model that makes use of auxiliary phrases to improve aspect-awareness and full BERT pre-training, in order to address these problems. It is also suggested that post-training domain expertise be acquired. Through the use of appropriate auxiliary phrases, experimental results on benchmark datasets show that BERT4ABSA outperforms conventional feature-based and standalone BERT algorithms, reaching cutting-edge performance that can be further improved through post-training with domain-specific data.[9]

Arfinda Ilmania et.al : Author study on word embeddings and aspect-text interactions are key components of the existing feature-based neural models for aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA), however they have limitations. The dataset consists of over 9,800 reviews that were collected from various categories on well-known Indonesian online marketplaces. The BERT4ABSA approach, which is built on auxiliary sentences for better aspect awareness and pre-training, is introduced in this study. It is also suggested that post-training domain expertise be acquired. Experiments show the greater performance of BERT4ABSA, which can be improved even further using domain-specific data. [10] Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) has various common themes and tendencies, as the table 1 analysis shows: For ABSA, researchers use a variety of datasets, such as those about restaurants, travel destinations, book reviews, cricket, bank service quality, and the influence of the airline business.

Table 1: Compilation of the most recent to the greatest work on Aspect based sentiment analysis

Sr.No	Author and year	Title	Dataset review	Techniques	Accuracy
11	Dian Arianto et.al. (2020)	Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis on Indonesia's Tourism Destinations Based on Google Maps User Code-Mixed Reviews (Study Case: Borobudur and Prambanan Temples)	we collected 5,592 reviews from Borobudur and Prambanan Temple by crawling them using BotSol's Google Maps Review Crawlers	Random Forest (RF), Naïve Bayes (NB), Logistic Regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT), and Extra Tree (ET).	74.4%(LR), 88.5%(DT) 88.1%(ET)
12	Kivanc Bayraktar et.al (2019)	A Rule-Based Holistic Approach for Turkish Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis	Turkish restaurant dataset	Rule-based approach	52,05%

13	ZHIYING REN et.al	A Lexicon-Enhanced Attention Network for Aspect-Level Sentiment Analysis	Restaurant, Laptop (SemEval-2014)	a Lexicon-Enhanced Attention Network based on n bidirectional LSTM	0.791(Restaurant) 0.737(Laptop)
14	Mohammad AL-Smadi et.al.	Human Annotated Arabic Dataset of Book Reviews for Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis	book reviews in Arabic language	BASELINE for Aspect Category Polarity	0.42
15	Forhad An Naim	Bangla Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Based On Corresponding Term Extraction	Cricket, restaurant dataset	Convolutional Neural Network	0.67
16	Elena Brunova et.al	Aspect Extraction and Sentiment Analysis in User Reviews in Russian about Bank Service Quality	reviews in Russian about bank service quality	rule-based, PMI	0.53, 0.640
17	Duc-Hong Pham et.al	Exploiting multiple word embeddings and one-hot character vectors for aspect-based sentiment analysis	52,574 reviews related to Price, Food, Service, Ambience, Anecdotes, and Miscellaneous	CNN	83.94
18	Yung-Chun Chang et.al	Predicting aspect-based sentiment using deep learning and information visualization: The impact of COVID-19 on the airline industry	review 191,123 for airline: January 2016–August 2020	deep learning and word embedding techniques,	-
19	Donatas Meškėlė et.al.	ALDONAr: A hybrid solution for sentence-level aspect-based sentiment analysis using a lexicalized domain ontology and a regularized neural attention model	SemEval 2014, SemEval 2015	ALDONAr	87.1, 83.8
20	Retno Kusumaningrum et.al	Deep learning-based application for multilevel sentiment analysis of Indonesian	hotel review documents from an OTA in Indonesian	CNN-based, LSTM-based	98.16%, 75.28%.

		hotel reviews	languages		
21	Satuluri Vanaja et.al	Aspect-Level Sentiment Analysis on E-Commerce Data	Amazon Customer Review Data	Naïve Bayes SVM	90.423% 83.43%
22	Md Shad Akhtar	Aspect based Sentiment Analysis in Hindi: Resource Creation and Evaluation	Hindi product reviews from web sources	CRF, SVM	Aspect: 41.07%, Sentiment: 54.05%
23	Abhilash Pathak	Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis in Hindi Language by Ensembling Pre-Trained mBERT Models	IIT-Patna Hindi Reviews dataset, Travel, Electronics ,Mobile Apps	Ensemble models based on mBERT	Cutting-edge Result 70.49%, (Electronics) , 48.78% (Mobile Apps), 75.47% (Travel) and 79.77% (Movies)
24	Md. Atikur Rahman	-	Customer reviews of restaurants, human-annotated user comments on cricket	Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random forest (RF) ,K-nearest neighbor (KNN)	-
25	Choirul Huda	Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis in Tourism Industry for Tourism Recommender System	Customer reviews from Trip Advisor	Machine learning algorithms (DT, RFC, SVM, XGBoost)	Accuracy specified

As per table 1 Various methodologies are used in different studies, such as deep learning, lexicon-enhanced attention networks, rule-based systems, and ensemble methods. This is a reflection of the continuous investigation of various sentiment analysis approaches. The studies' claimed accuracy scores differ greatly from one another. Some have modest outcomes (52.05% and 0.42%), while some reach excellent accuracy (98.16% and 83.94%). This demonstrates the difficulties and intricacies of ABSA, which can result in a range of performance outcomes. Several studies highlight the importance of sentiment analysis in a variety of linguistic contexts and the worldwide applicability of ABSA by concentrating on non-English languages like Turkish, Arabic, Bangla, and Russian. Applications of ABSA include book reviews, food service, tourism, and analysis of the airline business. This demonstrates how ABSA may adjust to different business areas. Certain research suggest hybrid solutions that integrate multiple methods, such deep learning and lexicalized domain ontologies, demonstrating the investigation of novestrategies to enhance ABSA accuracy. From a few thousand evaluations to over 190,000, the size of the datasets employed varies greatly; larger datasets may allow for more thorough research. There are situations where precise accuracy results are not given, which highlights the necessity of thorough reporting in research projects.

III. Feature Extraction Techniques:

Figure 2: Feature Extraction Techniques

- a. **Part of Speech Tagging:** The reviews need to be processed and given the proper parts of speech tags in order to retrieve important details like aspects and opinions. The process of part-of-speech (POS) tagging entails linguistic tag assignment based on word analysis inside a sentence.[4] A list of these linguistic POS tags is shown in Table .

Table 2.Part-of-speech (POS) tagging:

Tag	Description
RB	Adverb
NNPS	Proper noun, plura
NNS /NNP	Noun, plural noun, singular
VBZ	Verb, 3rd-person singular present
VBP	Verb, non-3rd-person singular/p
VBN	Verb, past participle
VBG	Verb, gerund, or present participle
VBD	Verb, past tense
VB	Verb, base form
RBS	Superlative adverb
RBR	Comparative adverb
JJ	Adjective
JJR	Comparative adjective
JJS	Superlative adjective
LS	List item marker

b. Pointwise Mutual Information (PMI):

PMI (Pointwise Mutual Information) serves as a metric for assessing the association between two terms. The PMI formula, presented below, measures this association:

$$\text{PMI}(\text{word1}, \text{word2}) = \log_2 \left[\frac{P(\text{word1}, \text{word2})}{P(\text{word1}) * P(\text{word2})} \right]$$

In this equation, $P(\text{word1}, \text{word2})$ signifies the probability of both word1 and word2 co-occurring, while $P(\text{word1}) * P(\text{word2})$ denotes the probability of their co-occurrence under statistical independence [30]. To compute the PMI score, Turney introduced the following equations :

1. $P(\text{word}) = \text{hits}(\text{word}) / N$ (2)
2. $P(\text{word1}, \text{word2}) = \text{hits}(\text{near}(\text{word1}, \text{word2})) / N$ (3)

Here, $\text{hits}(X)$ represents the frequency of occurrence of the word X , and $\text{near}(Y, Z)$ signifies noun groups within a specific distance, spanning from Y to Z . The hit function plays a pivotal role in the WSBFE (Web-Scale Bigrams from the Web) approach [12].

c. TF-IDF :

To assess a phrase's significance in a text and its rarity over the full corpus, Term Frequency-Inverse text Frequency (TF-IDF) is a frequently used technique. The resulting TF-IDF scores for each term in each tweet are combined into a feature vector, which functions as a representation of the tweet in the machine learning sentiment analysis process. Machine learning algorithms can then use this feature vector as an input [29].

d. Conditional random fields:

Every point in phase space in a random field has a random value that is selected based on a certain kind of distribution. Random variable sequences that meet the condition that the distribution at time $N+1$ is independent of the random variable values prior to time N and are arranged chronologically are said to exhibit the Markov property. Random fields with Markovian properties are called Markov random fields. The discriminant probability model serves as the foundation for conditional random fields. Let X and Y be random variables. Let Y be made up of an undirected graph, $G=(V, E)$, and $P(Y|X)$ be the conditional probability distribution of Y given X . Equation (1) defines the Markov property that these variables adhere to.

$$P(Y_v|X, Y_w, w \neq v) = P(Y_v|X, Y_w, w \sim v) \quad (1)$$

Where Y_v and Y_w represent two random variables that are placed at nodes v and w , respectively, and $w \sim v$ indicates all the w nodes related to v . A CRF is represented by the conditional probability distribution $P(Y|X)$ for the nodes v . We will now concentrate on linear-chain CRFs since they are used in this paper. Assume that there are two linear chains of random variables, $X = (X_1, X_2, \dots$ and $Y = (Y_1, Y_2, \dots$ and $Y_n)$; the sequence of Y

for a given random variable equals X . This series of random variables' conditional probability distribution $P(Y|X)$ satisfies the aforementioned Markov property defined in Eq. (2), making it a CRF.

$$P(Y_i | X, Y_1, \dots, Y_{i-1}, Y_{i+1}, \dots, Y_n) = P(Y_i | X, Y_{i-1}, Y_{i+1}) \quad (2)$$

Where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ (only one additional node is taken into account whether $i = 1$ or n). With X representing the input observation sequence and Y representing the matching output or state sequence, the distribution $P(Y|X)$ forms a linear-chain CRF [30].

e. Hidden Markov Models:

A statistical Markov model known as a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) operates under the assumption that the system it studies is a Markov process with hidden states that are not readily visible. The probability distribution across a set of possible sequences is described by this model, which is an organised probabilistic representation. HMMs can be thought of as a general mixing model plus a transition matrix combined. Starting from some initial states with associated probabilities, a series of states is produced by switching between states according to state-transition probabilities. This process keeps going until a final state is attained, at which point an observable series of symbols is produced. When a state is visited, a symbol is released. The hidden states together represent a Markov chain whose transition probabilities follow the Markov property, meaning that the hidden states are memoryless and only rely on the previous event. This effectively indicates that, regardless of all previous observations, the distribution of predictions for the next observation in a series depends only on the value of the observation that came right before it [31].

f. Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA):

The generative probabilistic model known as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) is used to analyse corpora. It describes documents essentially as stochastic mixtures of latent topics, where each topic is described by a distribution of words. The bag of words (BoW) strategy is used by LDA as a topic modelling tool to uncover hidden themes in the dataset [27]. The terms inside each topic with the highest likelihood provide insightful information about the meaning of the topic [28]. BoW increases computational effectiveness at the expense of leaving out inter-word semantic links. The dataset was expanded to include frequently used noun categories in order to lessen the restrictions given by BoW, and then the LDA model was utilised.

g. Dependency parser:

Wu et al. (2009) defined Phrase Dependency Parsing as a method for extracting relationships between product attributes and opinion terms. The dependency parser created a tree that connected words in a sentence, representing relationships between different phrases. The author's extracted aspects and opinion words from product reviews and discovered that 98% of product aspects in any review set were noun or verb phrase. To preserve precision, noun and verb phrases were retrieved as candidate aspects, while other phrases were discarded [34]. Aspects with low criteria were eliminated. To extract sentiment-representing opinion words, a dictionary-based technique was used. The authors employed a dependency parser to discover relationships between aspects and opinions, assuming that opinion words are frequently found near aspect terms. To find relationships between attributes and opinions, a new tree kernel was built and integrated with SVM.

The authors found the lowest common parent among all conceivable sub trees, with a maximum distance of 5 between aspect and opinion words inside one tree. This sub tree showed the relationship in a sentence between aspect and opinion words. In a related study, Yu et al. (2011a) extracted aspects from reviews using the phrase dependency parser (Wu et al. 2009). They used a list of advantages and drawbacks to construct a list of attributes, rating them based on frequency and user feedback.[35] To give weights to commonly cited characteristics by users and the sum of weights of opinion words used against distinct aspects of a product, a probabilistic regression technique was devised[36].

IV. Sentiment classification technique

Figure 3: Sentiment Classification Techniques

a. Machine Learning Approach

Sentiment analysis, or the classification of sentiments, is a task that machine learning algorithms can perform. This entails using techniques from natural language processing, text analysis, computational linguistics, and related fields to identify and quantify the emotional tone of text or voice. The procedure entails gathering information from social media platforms. By treating sentiment classification as a standard text classification problem, the machine learning technique takes into account linguistic and/or syntactic features. Using this method, the categorization model associates one of the predetermined class labels with the features of the input document. The model is then applied to forecast a class label for an unidentified instance. The problem occurs when an instance has only one label assigned to it, creating a tough classification situation. On the other hand, a soft classification problem is one in which an instance is assigned a probabilistic value of labels. Systems can learn new capabilities without explicit programming thanks to machine learning. Through machine learning, sentiment analysis algorithms can be trained to comprehend context, recognise sarcasm, and evaluate subtle word usage, going beyond simple definitions [32].

b. Lexicon based Approach

By consulting lexicons or dictionaries that assign polarity and strength values to words depending on their meanings, one can ascertain the semantic orientation of a text and determine if it has a positive, negative, or neutral mood. These dictionaries can be automatically constructed using seed words, or they can be manually curated. In this regard, lexicons like SentiWordNet, Linguistic Enquiry and Word Count (LIWC), and General Inquirer are frequently used. Although this approach is quite simple to use, it has trouble capturing the nuances of spoken language. For example, if we use a lexical approach to the statement "I didn't like headphones," the word "like" would be assessed as expressing a positive sentiment, which is not the intended sentiment [33].

V. Dissuasion

The studies given Experiment with a diverse range of datasets and techniques used in aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) research. Datasets range from specialised areas such as Indonesian vacation attractions, Turkish restaurants, and Arabic book reviews to broader domains such as the quality of Russian bank services and Amazon e-commerce. These datasets are rich sources of user-generated content, allowing researchers to examine feelings in a variety of contexts and languages. The techniques used range from traditional machine learning algorithms like Random Forest, Naïve Bayes, and Logistic Regression to more complex methods like convolutional neural networks (CNN), bidirectional LSTM networks, and ensemble models based on mBERT. The technique chosen is typically determined by the dataset's complexity and the required level of accuracy. CNNs, for example, are effective at extracting contextual information from textual data, whereas ensemble models such as mBERT can use pre-trained language representations to achieve cutting-edge performance across various domains. Overall, the utilisation of broad datasets and sophisticated methodologies highlights the changing environment of ABSA research, which seeks to extract nuanced sentiments from user-generated content across disciplines and languages.

VI. Conclusion

Sentiment analysis (SA) has evolved as a highly dynamic and increasingly popular subject within information retrieval and text mining, owing to the World's global spread. The research emphasise the need of addressing global context, domain-specific data, and auxiliary phrases in sentiment analysis to improve aspect-awareness. In this study we focus on various databases and approaches. According to reviews, this database contains more laptops, restaurants, and movies. As per this study three important techniques for feature extraction are usually used: TF-IDF, CRF, and POS. These well-known and effective procedures play an important role in extracting relevant features from textual data. Deep learning, SVM, Naive Bayes, and Random Forest all give good classification results.

VII. Reference

1. M. Abdul-Mageed, M. T. Diab and M. Korayem —Subjectivity and sentiment analysis of modern standard Arabic, In Proceedings of the 49th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies: short papers-Volume 2,2011
2. Mehta, P., & Pandya, D. (2020). A Review On Sentiment Analysis Methodologies, Practices And Applications. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 9, 601-609.
3. Ashmaki Suresh Waydande, Amol S. Dange,” Aspect based Sentiment Classification for Social Media Reviews using Supervised Classification Techniques”, - *Elementary Education Online* ,Vol 20 (Issue 5), 2021
4. Samha, Amani K., Yuefeng Li, and Jinglan Zhang. "Aspect-based opinion extraction from customer reviews." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1404.1982* (2014).
5. Hongjie Cai, Nan Song, Zengzhi Wang, Qiming Xie, Qiankun Zhao, Ke Li, Siwei Wu , Shijie Liu, Jianfei Yu, Rui Xia,” MEMD-ABSA: A Multi-Element Multi-Domain Dataset for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis”,2023
6. J. He, A. Wumaier, Z. Kadeer, W. Sun, X. Xin and L. Zheng, "A Local and Global Context Focus Multilingual Learning Model for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 84135-84146, 2022
7. Ahmad, Waqas and Khan, Hikmat and Alarfaj, Fawaz and Iqbal, Saqib and Alomair, Abdullah and Almusallam, Naif, “Aspect-Based Sentiment Classification Using Deep Learning and Hybrid of Word Embedding and Contextual Position”, *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, vol. 37, pp. 3101-3124,2023
8. JIANGTAO HE , AISHAN WUMAIER, ZAOKERE KADEER , WEIWEI SUN, XIANGZHE XIN, AND LINNA ZHENG, “A Local and Global Context Focus Multilingual Learning Model for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis”, *IEEE Access*, VOLUME 10, 2022 T
9. JINDIAN SU1 , SHANSHAN YU2,3, DA LUO.4,” Enhancing Aspect-based Sentiment Classification with Auxiliary Sentence and Domain Knowledge”, *IEEE Access*, VOLUME 4, 2016
10. A. Ilmania, Abdurrahman, S. Cahyawijaya and A. Purwarianti, "Aspect Detection and Sentiment Classification Using Deep Neural Network for Indonesian Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis," *2018 International Conference on Asian Language Processing (IEEE)*, Bandung, Indonesia, 2018, pp. 62-67
11. Dian Arianto and Indra Budi. 2020. Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis on Indonesia’s Tourism Destinations Based on Google Maps User Code-Mixed Reviews (Study Case: Borobudur and Prambanan Temples). In *Proceedings of the 34th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information and Computation*, pages 359–367, Hanoi, Vietnam. Association for Computational Linguistics.
12. K. Bayraktar, U. Yavanoglu and A. Ozbilen, "A Rule-Based Holistic Approach for Turkish Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis," *2019 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*, Los Angeles, CA, USA, 2019, pp. 2154-2158,
13. ZHIYING REN 1,3, GUANGPING ZENG 1,3, LIU CHEN 1,3, QINGCHUAN ZHANG 2 , CHUNGUANG ZHANG 1,3, AND DINGQI PAN,” A Lexicon-Enhanced Attention Network for Aspect-Level Sentiment Analysis”, *IEEE Access*, VOLUME 8, 2020

14. M. Al-Smadi, O. Qawasmeh, B. Talafha and M. Quwaider, "Human Annotated Arabic Dataset of Book Reviews for Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis," *2015 3rd International Conference on Future Internet of Things and Cloud*, Rome, Italy, 2015, pp. 726-730
15. Forhad An Naim," BANGLA ASPECT-BASED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS BASED ON CORRESPONDING TERM EXTRACTION", 2021 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology for Sustainable Development (ICICT4SD), 27-28 February, Dhaka, 2021
16. E. Brunova and Y. Bidulya, "Aspect Extraction and Sentiment Analysis in User Reviews in Russian about Bank Service Quality," *2017 IEEE 11th International Conference on Application of Information and Communication Technologies (AICT)*, pp. 1-4, Moscow, Russia, 2017,
17. Duc-Hong Pham a,c, Anh-Cuong Le," Exploiting multiple word embeddings and one-hot character vectors for aspect-based sentiment analysis ", *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning(ELSEVIER)*, 2018
18. Yung-Chun Chang b , Chih-Hao Ku a,* , Duy-Duc Le Nguyen," Predicting aspect-based sentiment using deep learning and information visualization: The impact of COVID-19 on the airline industry", *Information & Management(ELSEVIER)*,, 2021
19. Donatas Meškelė, Flavius Frasinca," ALDONAr: A hybrid solution for sentence-level aspect-based sentiment analysis using a lexicalized domain ontology and a regularized neural attention model", *Information Processing and Management(ELSEVIER)*,, 2020
20. Retno Kusumaningrum * , Iffa Zainan Nisa, Rahmat Jayanto, Rizka Putri Nawangsari, Adi Wibowo, "Deep learning-based application for multilevel sentiment analysis of Indonesian hotel reviews", *Heliyon(ELSEVIER)*, 2023
21. Satuluri Vanaja, Meena Belwal,|| Aspect-Level Sentiment Analysis on E-Commerce Datal, *International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA 2018)*.
22. Md Shad Akhtar, Asif Ekbal, and Pushpak Bhattacharyya. 2016. Aspect based Sentiment Analysis in Hindi: Resource Creation and Evaluation. In *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'16)*, pages 2703–2709
23. Pathak, Abhilash, Sudhanshu Kumar, Partha Pratim Roy, and Byung-Gyu Kim. 2021. "Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis in Hindi Language by Ensembling Pre-Trained mBERT Models" *Electronics* 10, no. 21: 2641
24. Md. Atikur Rahman and Emon Kumar Dey", *Datasets for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis in Bangla and Its Baseline Evaluation*",data, 4 May 2018
25. Choirul Huda; Yaya Heryadi; Lukas; Widodo Budiharto," Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis in Tourism Industry for Tourism Recommender System",2022 5th International Seminar on Research of Information Technology and Intelligent Systems (ISRITI) IEEE ,2022
26. K. W. Church and P. Hanks, "Word association norms, mutual information, and lexicography," *Computational linguistics*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 22-29, 1990
27. D. M. Blei, A. Y. Ng, and M. I. Jordan, "Latent dirichlet allocation," *Journal of machine Learning research*, vol. 3, no. Jan, pp. 993-1022, 2003.
28. Hamed Jelodar1 · Yongli Wang1,2 · Chi Yuan1 · Xia Feng1 · Xiahui Jiang1 · Yanchao Li1 · Liang Zhao1, "Latent dirichlet allocation (lda) and topic modeling: models, applications, a survey," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, pp. 1-43, 2018
29. Ahmed, Wesam & Semary, Noura & Amin, Khalid & Hammad, Mohamed. (2023). Sentiment Analysis on Twitter Using Machine Learning Techniques and TF-IDF Feature Extraction: A Comparative Study. *IJCI International Journal of Computers and Information*. 1. 10.21608/ijci.2023.236052.1128.
30. Huosong Xia1,3 · Yitai Yang1 · Xiaoting Pan1 · Zuopeng Zhang2 · Wuyue An1," Sentiment analysis for online reviews using conditional random fields and support vector machines", *Electronic Commerce Research*, (2020)
31. . Perikos, S. Kardakis, M. Paraskevas and I. Hatzilygeroudis, "Hidden Markov Models for Sentiment Analysis in Social Media," *2019 IEEE International Conference on Big Data, Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (BCD)*, Honolulu, HI, USA, 2019, pp. 130-135

32. Mayur Wankhade^{1,2} · Annavarapu Chandra Sekhara Rao^{1,2} · Chaitanya Kulkarni¹,” A survey on sentiment analysis methods, applications, and challenges”, *Artificial Intelligence Review* (2022)
33. Aman Mehto, Karnika Indras,” Data Mining through Sentiment Analysis: Lexicon based Sentiment Analysis Model using Aspect Catalogue”, 2016 Symposium on Colossal Data Analysis and Networking (CDAN)(IEEE), 2016
34. Wu Y, Zhang Q, Huang X, Wu L (2009) Phrase dependency parsing for opinion mining. In: Proceedings of the 2009 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing, Volume 3. Association for computational linguistics, pp 1533–1541
35. Yu J, Zha Z-J, Wang M, Chua T-S (2011a) Aspect ranking: identifying important product aspects from online consumer reviews. In: Proceedings of the 49th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics: human language technologies-Volume 1. Association for computational linguistics, pp 1496– 1505.
36. Toqir A. Rana¹ · Yu-N Cheah¹,” Aspect extraction in sentiment analysis: comparative analysis and survey”, *Artif Intell Rev* (2016)
37. Andi Suciati¹, Indra Budi²,” Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis and Emotion Detection for Code-Mixed Review”, *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, Vol. 11, No. 9, 2020
38. LunaDeBruyne^{1,*},AkbarKarimi^{2,*},Orph´eeDeClercq¹,AndreaPrati²,V´eroniqueHoste¹,” Aspect-Based Emotion Analysis and Multimodal Coreference: A Case Study of Customer Comments on Adidas Instagram Posts”, *Proceedings of the 13th Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation*, pages 574–580,2022
39. Choirul Huda; Yaya Heryadi; Lukas; Widodo Budiharto,” Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis in Tourism Industry for Tourism Recommender System“,2022 5th International Seminar on Research of Information Technology and Intelligent Systems (ISRITI) IEEE ,2022
40. Nadheesh Jihan,” Multi-Domain Aspect Extraction using Support Vector Machines,” *The 2017 Conference on Computational Linguistics and Speech Processing*, pp. 308-322, 2017
41. Tianyu Zhao, Junping Du, Zhe Xue, Ang Li, Zeli Guan,” Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis using Local Context Focus Mechanism with DeBERTa”, *Computation and Language*“,7 Jul 2022
42. . Wenxuan Zhang, Xin Li, Yang Deng, Lidong Bing, and Wai Lam,” A Survey on Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis: Tasks, Methods, and Challenges”, *IEEE*,2022
43. Thomas Gaillat, Bernardo Stearns, Gopal Sridhar,” Implicit and Explicit Aspect Extraction in Financial Micro blogs ”, *Proceedings of the First Workshop on Economics and Natural Language Processing*, pages 55–61, Australia, July 20, 2018
44. Soujanya Poria, Lun-WeiKu, ChenGui,” A Rule-Based Approach to Aspect Extraction from Product Reviews”, *Proceedings of the Second Workshop on Natural Language Processing for Social Media*, pages 28–37, Dublin, Ireland, August 24 2014.